

MANCHESTER
1824

The University of Manchester

OUR LIVES • OUR COMMUNITIES • OUR PHOTO BOOK

PICTURE US!

WEST CHESHIRE

MANCHESTER

DONCASTER

**In the summer of 2020,
during the COVID-19 lockdown,
researchers from The University of Manchester
ran a Facebook photo project in 15 areas of
Doncaster, North Manchester and West Cheshire.**

We wanted to create a fun, lock-down activity which helped us to find out what local people thought were the issues in their area related to health and wellbeing, digital life and financial life. It attracted a total of 441 group members, and 165 photos were posted. We hope that what we learnt will lead to future investment in projects that local people really want.

As a thank you to everyone who participated, we have produced this photobook which you are welcome to download and share.

HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING •

“ Spending time in green space or bringing nature into your everyday life can benefit both your mental and physical wellbeing. ”

“ And what better for the healthy development of young minds and bodies than play... and outdoor play in nature must surely be the very best play of all! ”

“ During lockdown it's been great that I've been able to shop online, especially for food as I've felt nervous going to supermarkets. Although can be frustrating when there's not been any available slots! ”

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 Thank you!!
 for working hard so we can stay safe & still receive our post!
 you are all heroes
 Stay Safe & well

HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

“ Digital Life... without the digital world I wouldn't have made over 200 new friends over lockdown. ”

“ The tree in the photo is old and gnarled, however there is signs of new growth. Nature carries on regardless. This gave me a feeling of hope, perhaps we will come out if this pandemic stronger and more appreciative of our natural environment.”

HEALTH AND WELL-BEING
HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

“ Gardening and growing my own plants has an amazing effect on me, it's calming, it gives me focus it takes me out of the busy day to day life, it's almost meditative, I feel relaxed and happy and I do call my allotment "my happy place". ”

“ Health and wellbeing is visiting my neighbour's allotment with my daughter, and returning with lovely flowers and produce. my neighbour grew them, and lots of vegetables too. ”

HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

“ In general it is difficult for people on low income to get access to good quality food, to get access to good quality exercise, to get access to social groups, toddler groups, groups for young people – everything comes at a cost. ”

HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING • HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

“ Health and wellbeing is visiting my neighbour's allotment with my daughter, and returning with lovely flowers and produce. my neighbour grew them, and lots of vegetables too. ”

“ whenever things seem too much i love to sit in the garden and look up at the sky, it helps to clear my mind and relax. ”

Picture Us Photobook

Produced as part of the PRIOR (Poverty Reduction's Influence On Risk factors for non-communicable diseases: a systems approach) project.

PRIOR aims to transform deprived communities in the north of England through interventions that empower individuals to escape debt and poverty, and improve their mental and physical health.

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